

THE TERNARY SYSTEM. POTASSIUM NITRATE, AMMONIUM NITRATE AND WATER AT 25°.

By R. K. BAHL AND SURJIT SINGH.

In the system $\text{KNO}_3\text{-NH}_4\text{NO}_3\text{-H}_2\text{O}$, studied at 25°, the two salts do not form any double salt or a salt hydrate.

The heterogeneous equilibria between the nitrates of potassium and ammonium was studied to determine the existence of any double salt formed and to investigate the change of the solubility of one in the presence of the other along with the nature of the solid phases present. The vapour phase has been assumed to be absent and the whole subject has been treated from the point of view of condensed system at atmospheric pressure.

To a definite amount of potassium nitrate, increasing amounts of ammonium nitrate were added in presence of a constant amount of water. The various complexes were vigorously stirred up to equilibrium in wide tubes immersed in a water thermostat kept at a constant temperature of 25°. The usual time given was 48 hours. When the equilibrium was established, the composition of the solution was determined by withdrawing portions of them by means of a pipette heated previously to the temperature of the bath. It was filtered and weighed in stoppered bottles and then analysed. The moist residue was weighed separately and analysed.

The ammonium ion was estimated by the usual distillation method and the nitrate was determined by Lunge's nitrometer as given by Scott ("Standard Methods of Chemical Analysis", 1925, Vol. I p. 353). The amounts of potassium and water were calculated by difference.

The system at 25° is shown in Fig. 1 and the data for this system at the above temperature is given below.

Composition by Weight.

KNO ₃	Solution.		Temperature = 25°		Solid phases
	NH ₄ NO ₃	o %	KNO ₃	Rest NH ₄ NO ₃	
27.1	o	%	—	—	KNO ₃
19.36	22.80		50.22%	14.25%	KNO ₃
16.56	31.784		58.15	16.31	KNO ₃
22.21	42.83		74.4	17.8	KNO ₃ , NH ₄ NO ₃
16.92	48.20		9.1	72.1	NH ₄ NO ₃
7.23	59.44		4.3	77.2	NH ₄ NO ₃
o	68.1		—	—	NH ₄ NO ₃

It is clear from the above that the system potassium nitrate-ammonium nitrate-water belongs to the simplest type of ternary system; neither double salts nor salt hydrates occur in it.

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
GOVERNMENT COLLEGE,
LAHORE.

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